
THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN JOURNALISM

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353730>

Nafosat Davlatova

Master's degree student

Journalism and Mass Communications University of Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the use of technologies based on artificial intelligence algorithms by the media. The principles of operation of machine learning, deep learning based on neural networks, and recommender systems are disclosed. An analytical review of the use of these technologies in such areas as data processing and analysis is made; automatic production of information about current events and facts (messages about emergencies, results of sports competitions, the course of election campaigns, etc.); interactive communication with the audience; tracking informational occasions; verification of facts for reliability (fact-checking); image recognition; production of video content, etc.

Keywords: *mass media, artificial intelligence, media, big data, information bubble, echo chamber, information dependence.*

INTRODUCTION

The modern media market is represented not only by the mass media and information consumers. In this market, a fundamentally new participant has emerged and every year occupies more and more space - artificial intelligence, which is changing the usual look of traditional journalism and reformatting the media space that was once familiar to us. If we represent the situation schematically, we will see a system in which not only the media communicate with the consumer, but the consumer communicates with the media; more and more artificial intelligence is involved in interaction with them. The functionality and significance of this kind of intermediary, as well as the process of formation and development of artificial intelligence in the media, require serious scientific study and reflection.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Modern mass media, more than ever, actively interact with the consumer of the mass media. With the advent of the Internet, this interaction is becoming increasingly interactive, and the media are turning into global media and mass communication. If

earlier the media user carried out feedback with them in the form of “letters to the editor”, now the range of such interaction has significantly expanded and changed qualitatively. It includes not only comments, likes, reposts, discussions in social networks (including those with the direct participation of the authors of information materials), but also the possibility for users to form their own news column, create content for Mass media by transferring photos, video and audio recordings from the scene, etc.

High-tech companies that are rapidly introducing artificial intelligence into the activities of modern media and fundamentally changing the practice of journalistic work, in fact, are becoming a new player in the field of mass media, turning the IT industry almost into the main figure in the media market, overshadowing such traditional and important participants as the state and big business [Mamedyarov Z.2019.P. 13–17.]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Be that as it may, the main components of what is currently called artificial intelligence are [2]:[Kurpatov A.V, 2019: 400]

- machine learning;
- deep learning based on neural networks;
- recommender systems.

Machine learning is one of the areas of development of artificial intelligence, the main principle of which is that machines receive data and learn from them, detecting certain patterns. This is the most promising tool for business, science and making important management decisions. Machine learning systems are able to quickly apply the knowledge gained from training on large datasets, which allows them to excel in solving problems such as face recognition, speech recognition, object recognition, translation, and many others. Unlike programs with manually coded instructions for performing specific tasks, machine learning allows the system to learn to recognize patterns and make predictions on its own [Miroshnichenko M.TextTerra, 2015]

Deep learning is a subset of machine learning. It applies some machine learning techniques to real world problems using neural networks that can mimic human decision making.

Neural networks arose as a result of research in the field of artificial intelligence, during which the idea arose to reproduce the ability of biological nervous systems to learn and correct errors by modeling the low-level structure of the brain.

Table 1

Examples of technologies using artificial intelligence and their scope in journalism [4][M. Miroshnichenko. 2015.]

Technology developer	Media using this technology	Scope of technology
Reuters News Tracer / Thomson Reuters	Reuters	Track the main events of the day on social networks and check the validity of messages on Twitter
Wordsmith Automated Insights	Associated Press	Creation of reports based on financial data
Heliograf / The Washington Post	The Washington Post	Coverage of sports events and election campaigns
Perspective API (Alphabet / Google)	The New York Times	Moderating reader comments
Reuters Connect	Reuters	The platform displays all Reuters content, including the archive, as well as content from media partners around the world in real time
Newswhip	Associated Press	The program tracks the distribution of any content on the seven largest social platforms within minutes of posting and allows you to predict what will excite the audience in the near future

When discussing the advantages of journalists over artificial intelligence, they often point out that only a professional person is able to bring context or emotional evaluation into the text, which is partly confirmed by some studies. For example, in the US and Germany, groups of journalists were shown a large number of articles in English and German, respectively. Half of the texts were written by people, half by machines. On average, people could not tell them apart, and when subjects were asked to categorize texts according to their credibility and interest, they found machine-written texts to be more credible. At the same time, the respondents noted that reading them is not as interesting as “human” articles.

In China, Jinri Toutiao (meaning "Today's Headlines") is the leader among software products that use artificial intelligence to algorithmize and edit news. Toutiao's artificial intelligence engines search the Internet for content using natural language processing and computer vision tools to analyze content from a wide network of partner sites and approved sources. They then draw on their users' past

behavior—their clicks, read data, opinions, comments, and so on—to create personalized news tailored to each individual's interests. The app's algorithms even change titles to increase clicks. And the more those clicks, the more accurately Toutiao will offer them the content they want to see. This positive feedback has resulted in one of the most sought-after content platforms on the web, with users spending an average of 74 minutes a day on the app [E.A.Smirnova, A.P.Sukhodolov, 2018. 200]. Thus, the involuntary attention of the user is exchanged by the media for advertising money, and advertising - taking into account modern advances in the field of targeting - hits the target. Information has become an easily accessible and practically legal drug, and its addressees pay the price by turning into ideal consumers.

CONCLUSION

The speed of creating new products and solutions is growing exponentially, and if someone can provide a monopoly in artificial intelligence, he will become the ruler of the world. But the media, together with the state and civil society, have yet to think about what the consequences of owning this new perfect tool can lead to.

REFERENCES

1. Mamedyarov Z. Dictatorship of platforms / Z. Mamedyarov // *Expert*. - 2019. - No. 28. - P. 13–17.
2. Kurpatov A.V. Fourth World War. The future is near! / A.V. Kurpatov. - St. Petersburg, 2019. - 400 p.
3. Gurova T. Hack humanity / T. Gurova // *Expert*. - 2019. - No. 3. - P. 40–48.
4. Miroschnichenko M. Robot-journalism: robots work hard - is a person happy? / M. Miroschnichenko // *TexTerra*. — 2015.
5. Social risk factors for Internet addiction: monograph / T.N. Svetlichnaya, E.A. Smirnova, A.P. Sukhodolov [and others]; ed. G.A. Kovaleva, A.A. Fur. - Cherepovets: Publishing house of ChSU, 2018. - 200 p.
6. Chetverikova O. Transhumanism in Russian education. Our children as a commodity / O. Chetverikova. - Moscow: Prince. world, 2018. - 384 p.